

Viscometric and thermodynamic study of bi-univalent mixed electrolyte systems in non-aqueous solvents at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K

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Abstract : Viscosities (η) and apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of solutions of bi-univalent mixed electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents, formamide (FA), dimethyl formamide (DMF) and dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO), have been determined at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K. From these data the values of coefficients A and B of Jones-Dole equation and that of V_ϕ^0 and S_v of Masson's equation have been obtained. Besides, the activation thermodynamic quantities ($\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$, $\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$) of viscous flow have also been calculated for the mixed electrolyte systems in these non-aqueous solvents. The values of A , B , V_ϕ^0 and S_v and those of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$, $\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ have also been determined for individual bi-univalent electrolytes in FA, DMF and DMSO.

Keywords : Viscosities, molar volumes, mixed electrolyte, non-aqueous solvents.

The studies of thermodynamic properties of aqueous mixed electrolytic solutions using the Mayer-McMillan theory as developed by Friedman and Anderson have been found to be useful in understanding the specific ion-ion interactions in solutions^{1,2}. Relative viscosities of ternary aqueous mixed electrolytic solutions for the systems KBr-NaBr, KBr-Bu₄NBr, NaCl-NaBr and NaCl-Bu₄NBr at constant ionic strength with varying electrolyte mole fractions at 25 °C have been determined^{3,4}.

Literature contains numerous studies on viscometric and thermodynamic studies on mixed electrolyte systems comprising compressibility, sound velocity etc.⁵⁻⁸.

Viscometric and thermodynamic studies of mixed electrolyte systems in regard to ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions in non-aqueous solvents are still lacking. Comprehensive studies on the viscometric and thermodynamic behavior of solutions of the following bi-univalent mixed electrolytes in formamide (FA), dimethyl formamide (DMF), dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO), as noted against their names, have been undertaken at different temperatures :

(i) BaCl₂ + MgCl₂ (FA); (ii) SrCl₂ + BaCl₂ (FA); (iii) CoCl₂ + BaCl₂ (FA); (iv) CoCl₂ + MgCl₂ (FA); (v) SrCl₂ + MgCl₂ (FA); (vi) SrCl₂ + CoCl₂ (FA); (vii) NiCl₂ + BaCl₂ (DMSO); (viii) HgCl₂ + NiCl₂ (DMSO);

(ix) CoCl₂ + HgCl₂ (DMSO); (x) NiCl₂ + MnCl₂ (DMSO); (xi) SnCl₂ + NiCl₂ (DMSO); (xii) HgCl₂ + MnCl₂ (DMSO); (xiii) CoCl₂ + SnCl₂ (DMSO); (xiv) NiCl₂ + SrCl₂ (DMSO); (xv) SrCl₂ + HgCl₂ (DMSO); (xvi) MnCl₂ + SrCl₂ (DMSO); (xvii) SnCl₂ + HgCl₂ (DMSO); (xviii) NiCl₂ + CoCl₂ (DMSO); (xix) MnCl₂ + CoCl₂ (DMF); (xx) NiCl₂ + CoCl₂ (DMF); (xxi) ZnCl₂ + CoCl₂ (DMF); (xxii) ZnCl₂ + NiCl₂ (DMF); (xxiii) SnCl₂ + CoCl₂ (DMF); (xxiv) ZnCl₂ + SnCl₂ (DMF) and (xxv) SnCl₂ + NiCl₂ (DMF).

Objectives of the present work are :

- (i) Determination of densities and viscosities of solutions of bi-univalent mixed electrolytes in FA, DMF and DMSO at different temperatures as a function of y , the fraction of ionic strength due to the first electrolyte in the mixture of two electrolytes, keeping the ionic strength constant;
- (ii) Determination of densities and viscosities of single bi-univalent electrolyte systems as a function of molar concentration (C) under the same experimental conditions as were maintained in mixed electrolyte systems;
- (iii) Analysis of viscosity data in the light of Jones-Dole equation for mixed and single electrolyte systems separately;

- (iv) Determination of apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of the mixed electrolytes systems at different temperatures in non-aqueous solvents as a function of y , keeping the ionic strength constant and then to analysis $V_\phi - y$ data in the light of Masson's equation;
- (v) Determination of V_ϕ of bi-univalent single electrolyte systems as a function of C in non-aqueous solvents at different temperature and analysis of $V_\phi - C$ data in the light of Masson's equation and
- (vi) Determination of free energies of activation of viscous flow $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$, per mole of solvent and solute respectively, and the subsequent determination of entropy of activation ($\Delta S_2^{0\#}$) and enthalpy of activation ($\Delta H_2^{0\#}$) of the viscous flow process of solutions of bi-univalent mixed and single electrolyte systems at different temperatures in non-aqueous solvents.

$$\text{or, } \frac{(\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1)}{\sqrt{C}} = A + B\sqrt{C} \quad (2)$$

where η and η_0 are the viscosities of the solution and solvent respectively. The coefficient A in this equation is a measure of solute-solute (ion-ion) interaction, whereas the coefficient B is a measure of solute-solvent (ion-solvent) interaction.

The relative viscosity of the mixed electrolytes system can be expressed in terms of y , the fraction of ionic strength due to first electrolyte in a mixture of two electrolytes. Thus replacing C by y , eq. (2) becomes

$$\frac{(\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1)}{\sqrt{y}} = A + B\sqrt{y} \quad (3)$$

The densities and viscosities of solutions of bi-univalent single and mixed electrolytes systems in FA, DMF and DMSO have been determined at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K as a function of C and y respectively. The viscosity data of single and mixed electrolytes systems have been analyzed in the light of eqs. (2) and (3) respectively. The values of coefficients A and B in single and mixed electrolyte systems have been obtained from the linear plots of $(\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ versus \sqrt{C} and $(\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1)/\sqrt{y}$ versus \sqrt{y} respectively by the method of least squares and the values are listed in Tables 1 and 2. It is seen that

Results and discussion

The concentration dependence of relative viscosity of an electrolyte solution is represented by Jones-Dole equation⁹ :

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = \eta_{\text{rel}} = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (1)$$

Table 1. Values of coefficients A and B of Jones-Dole equation for bi-univalent single electrolyte systems in FA, DMF and DMSO at different temperatures

Electrolyte	A (dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-1/2})			B (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
BaCl ₂ (FA)	-0.5125	-0.5126	-0.5128	0.2250	0.2170	0.2100
MgCl ₂ (FA)	-0.5160	-0.5175	-0.5180	0.3960	0.3880	0.3790
CoCl ₂ (FA)	-0.5126	-0.5425	-0.5735	0.3850	0.3760	0.3670
SrCl ₂ (FA)	-0.5128	-0.5144	-0.5236	0.2740	0.2680	0.2610
BaCl ₂ (DMSO)	-0.8077	-0.8103	-0.8120	0.2200	0.2130	0.2050
NiCl ₂ (DMSO)	-0.7943	-0.8074	-0.8216	0.3900	0.3830	0.3750
HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	-0.8095	-0.8102	-0.8105	0.1150	0.1080	0.1020
SnCl ₂ (DMSO)	-0.7989	-0.8104	-0.8110	0.2840	0.2770	0.2650
SrCl ₂ (DMSO)	-0.8102	-0.8105	-0.8110	0.2720	0.2650	0.2580
MnCl ₂ (DMSO)	-0.8103	-0.8106	-0.8111	0.3880	0.3820	0.3750
CoCl ₂ (DMSO)	-0.7498	-0.8104	-0.8110	0.3830	0.3760	0.3720
CoCl ₂ (DMF)	-0.8125	-0.8137	-0.8141	0.3800	0.3730	0.3660
MnCl ₂ (DMF)	-0.8110	-0.8130	-0.8142	0.3850	0.3770	0.3710
ZnCl ₂ (DMF)	-0.8124	-0.8127	-0.8129	0.3690	0.3620	0.3540
NiCl ₂ (DMF)	-0.8121	-0.8124	-0.8126	0.3860	0.3780	0.3700
SnCl ₂ (DMF)	-0.8120	-0.8126	-0.8123	0.2810	0.2750	0.2630

Table 2. Values of coefficients *A* and *B* of Jones-Dole equation for bi-univalent mixed electrolyte systems in FA, DMF and DMSO at different temperatures

Mixed electrolyte system	Ionic strength (<i>I</i>)	<i>A</i> (dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-1/2})			<i>B</i> (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)		
		293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
BaCl ₂ + MgCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	1.0691	1.0066	1.0158	-0.8954	-0.9526	-0.9856
SrCl ₂ + BaCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	1.1122	0.9873	1.0417	-0.6392	-0.6677	-0.7509
CoCl ₂ + BaCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	1.0992	0.9857	1.0344	-0.6652	-0.7144	-0.7931
CoCl ₂ + MgCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	0.9618	0.9102	0.8025	-0.4816	-0.6087	-0.6704
SrCl ₂ + MgCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	0.9261	0.8926	0.8343	-0.3822	-0.4682	-0.5418
SrCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	1.4401	1.4626	1.4984	-1.0892	-1.1073	-1.1248
NiCl ₂ + BaCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	0.5374	0.8184	0.9473	-0.5050	-0.7667	-0.8591
HgCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	0.3550	0.5556	0.9475	-0.2363	-0.3132	-0.6849
CoCl ₂ + HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	0.5820	0.9104	1.1141	-0.5552	-0.8505	-0.9171
NiCl ₂ + MnCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	0.1267	0.3016	0.6175	-0.1199	-0.1735	-0.2629
SnCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	0.1487	0.3089	0.0535	-0.4242	-0.6895	-0.9614
HgCl ₂ + MnCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	0.0212	0.3746	0.1680	-0.1351	-0.1638	-0.2139
CoCl ₂ + SnCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	0.0257	0.1846	0.5630	-0.1411	-0.2691	-0.3729
NiCl ₂ + SrCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	0.4389	0.7494	1.1056	-0.4242	-0.6875	-0.9614
SrCl ₂ + HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	0.5809	0.9107	0.6344	-0.5024	-0.5809	-0.8071
MnCl ₂ + SrCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	0.4025	0.6679	0.6966	-0.4454	-0.5270	-0.6587
SnCl ₂ + HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	0.5795	0.8828	1.1296	-0.5895	-0.8708	-1.2512
NiCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	0.2708	0.5196	0.7616	-0.1930	-0.3905	-0.5776
MnCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	0.3220	0.3057	0.3581	-0.4063	-0.4318	-0.4711
NiCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	0.2510	0.2232	0.2132	-0.1212	-0.2095	-0.3268
ZnCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	0.0877	0.3928	0.6319	-0.4248	-0.5091	-0.7556
ZnCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	0.5480	0.5998	0.9232	-0.6013	-0.7634	-1.0262
SnCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	0.4041	0.5369	0.6283	-0.4944	-0.5998	-0.7012
ZnCl ₂ + SnCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	0.3847	0.5319	0.5321	-0.4822	-0.6057	-0.6227
SnCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	0.1851	0.0037	0.0019	-0.0812	-0.1812	-0.2366

the values of *A* are negative in the case of solutions of single electrolyte systems in all the non-aqueous solvents used, while the values of *B* are positive. On the other hand, for mixed electrolytes systems the values of *A* are positive in all the non-aqueous solvents used while the values of *B* are negative. The negative values of *A* in the case of single electrolyte systems indicate^{10,11} the presence of very weak ion-ion interactions in FA, DMF and DMSO, while the positive values of *B* suggest the presence of strong ion-solvent¹² interactions. On the other hand, in the case of mixed electrolytes systems the values of *A* are positive, while those of *B* are negative. From this it follows that in mixed electrolytes systems the ion-ion interactions become strong¹³, while those of ion-solvent interactions are rendered weak¹⁴. This may be attributed to the effect of ionic strength of the medium, which facilitates ion-pair formation resulting in cation-

anion interactions. In the case of single electrolyte systems, the latter situation does not arise owing to the fact that the values of *A* correspond to the condition when \sqrt{C} is zero, that is the values of *A* in the case of single electrolyte systems correspond to zero ionic strength of the medium. In the case of mixed electrolytes systems, however, the values of *A* correspond to the condition when \sqrt{y} is zero (hence $y = 0$), that is the fraction of ionic strength due to first electrolyte in the mixture of two electrolytes is zero. But the system does possess a constant value of ionic strength due to the contribution of the ions of second electrolyte. Thus, for example, the value of *A* for the mixed systems : BaCl₂ + MgCl₂ in FA at constant ionic strength $I = 1.5$ (Table 2) corresponds to the situation when $\sqrt{y} = 0$ (and hence $y = 0$), but still the ionic strength of the medium is 1.5 which is due to the ions of second electrolyte (MgCl₂).

For a single electrolyte system the concentration dependence of apparent molar volume (V_ϕ) is given by the Masson's equation¹⁵,

$$V_\phi = V_\phi^0 + S_v\sqrt{C} \quad (4)$$

where V_ϕ^0 is called the limiting apparent molar volume and is equal to the partial molar volume, V_2^0 of the solute at infinite dilution. V_ϕ^0 is related to ion-solvent interaction and S_v is the experimental slope, dependent on charge and type of the electrolyte and is related to ion-ion interaction. The values of V_ϕ^0 and S_v for single electrolyte systems have been obtained by least square fit of $V_\phi - C$ data in eq. (4) and are listed in Table 3.

The eq. (4) has been applied to the present case of bi-univalent mixed electrolytes systems where the plots of V_ϕ versus y have been found to be linear while those of V_ϕ versus \sqrt{y} are found to be non-linear. From this it follows that for solutions of bi-univalent mixed electrolytes systems in non-aqueous solvents of FA, DMF and DMSO, the variation of V_ϕ with y i.e. fraction of the ionic strength due to the first electrolyte in the mixture of two electrolytes, at different temperatures is linear and that it is governed by the following modified form of Masson's equation,

$$V_\phi = V_\phi^0 + S_v y \quad (5)$$

The apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of solutions of bi-univalent mixed electrolytes in FA, DMF and DMSO have been determined as a function of y at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K, keeping the ionic strength constant. The values of V_ϕ^0 and S_v have been determined by the computerized least square fit of $V_\phi - y$ data in eq. (5) and are listed in Table 4.

The values of V_ϕ^0 are largely positive for all the bi-univalent single electrolyte systems (Table 3) and tend to decrease with the rise of temperature. From this it follows that ion-solvent interactions in non-aqueous solvents are strong and tend to become less stronger at elevated temperatures. On the other hand, the values of S_v are largely negative which indicate the presence of weak ion-ion interactions.

In the case of mixed bi-univalent electrolytes systems, the values of V_ϕ^0 are negative, while those of S_v are positive. This shows the presence of weak ion-solvent and strong ion-ion interactions in the solutions of bi-univalent mixed electrolytes systems in non-aqueous media at constant ionic strength.

From the foregoing discussion it is concluded that viscometric and volumetric data lead to the identical conclusions in regard to ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions in bi-univalent single and mixed electrolytes systems.

The viscosity data have also been analysed on the basis of transition state treatment of relative viscosity of electrolytic solutions as suggested by Feakins *et al.*¹⁶.

Table 3. Values of limiting apparent molar volume (V_ϕ^0) and experimental slope (S_v) for bi-univalent single electrolyte systems in FA, DMF and DMSO at different temperatures

Electrolyte	V_ϕ^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)			S_v (cm ³ dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-3/2})		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
BaCl ₂ (FA)	25.08	24.29	23.56	-58.60	-58.02	-57.25
MgCl ₂ (FA)	17.22	16.78	16.03	-44.16	-44.12	-40.50
CoCl ₂ (FA)	15.24	14.75	14.12	-42.96	-42.10	-41.46
SrCl ₂ (FA)	19.62	19.14	18.44	-52.39	-51.90	-51.47
BaCl ₂ (DMSO)	27.35	26.70	25.94	-124.28	-125.16	-128.01
NiCl ₂ (DMSO)	15.25	14.35	13.56	-118.68	-119.47	-122.31
HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	19.37	18.69	18.03	-150.22	-151.13	-154.38
SnCl ₂ (DMSO)	20.22	19.45	18.65	-107.63	-108.02	-110.71
SrCl ₂ (DMSO)	20.65	20.00	19.28	-146.07	-146.97	-150.16
MnCl ₂ (DMSO)	23.55	24.38	24.69	-151.49	-152.27	-154.61
CoCl ₂ (DMSO)	14.88	14.12	13.22	-118.23	-119.03	-121.85
CoCl ₂ (DMF)	14.56	13.65	13.05	-154.00	-155.63	-158.02
MnCl ₂ (DMF)	22.27	21.59	21.05	-111.37	-111.74	-114.18
ZnCl ₂ (DMF)	16.33	15.75	15.15	-104.49	-105.15	-106.41
NiCl ₂ (DMF)	15.50	14.89	14.16	-157.90	-155.68	-157.90
SnCl ₂ (DMF)	21.56	19.85	19.21	-142.82	-142.34	-144.44

Table 4. Values of limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}^0) and experimental slope (S_v) for bi-univalent mixed electrolyte systems in non-aqueous media at different temperatures

Mixed electrolyte system	Ionic strength (I)	V_{ϕ}^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)			S_v (cm ³ dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-3/2})		
		293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
BaCl ₂ + MgCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-7.10	-7.14	-7.15	1.67	1.70	1.71
SrCl ₂ + BaCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-8.54	-8.55	-8.57	0.82	0.83	0.92
CoCl ₂ + BaCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-9.08	-8.60	-8.62	0.82	0.23	0.23
CoCl ₂ + MgCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-7.11	-7.12	-7.13	1.32	1.35	1.39
SrCl ₂ + MgCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-7.19	-7.20	-7.21	2.06	2.08	2.10
SrCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-8.35	-9.25	-8.53	0.78	0.86	1.01
NiCl ₂ + BaCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-75.30	-75.58	-76.55	2.56	2.57	2.60
HgCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-72.26	-54.91	-73.88	10.65	10.82	11.58
CoCl ₂ + HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-83.49	-83.79	-84.87	10.10	10.13	10.26
NiCl ₂ + MnCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-61.07	-61.30	-62.09	11.72	11.76	11.92
SnCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-69.12	-69.51	-70.05	3.75	3.80	3.92
HgCl ₂ + MnCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-60.76	-61.11	-53.56	22.95	24.58	27.64
CoCl ₂ + SnCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-69.46	-69.71	-70.61	3.59	3.61	3.65
NiCl ₂ + SrCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-82.00	-82.30	-83.36	9.01	9.04	9.16
SrCl ₂ + HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-83.50	-83.89	-84.97	1.01	1.39	1.41
MnCl ₂ + SrCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-81.91	-82.21	-83.27	20.89	20.96	21.23
SnCl ₂ + HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-83.71	-84.02	-85.10	14.37	14.42	14.61
NiCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-73.01	-73.28	-74.22	0.15	0.17	0.19
MnCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-85.20	-85.59	-86.33	14.53	14.59	14.72
NiCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-84.98	-85.37	-86.11	0.15	0.17	0.19
ZnCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-85.26	-85.65	-86.39	36.73	36.89	37.21
ZnCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-84.81	-85.35	-86.09	36.37	36.71	37.03
SnCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-85.32	-85.44	-86.15	3.83	4.21	4.24
ZnCl ₂ + SnCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-80.64	-81.03	-81.71	31.93	32.07	32.35
SnCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-84.96	-85.35	-86.09	4.35	4.37	4.41

The coefficient B of the Jones-Dole equation is related to the free energy of activation by the following equation,

$$B = \frac{\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0}{1000} + \frac{\bar{V}_1^0}{1000} [(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#})/RT] \quad (6)$$

where \bar{V}_1^0 is the mean volume of the solvent and \bar{V}_2^0 is the partial molar volume of the solute, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ is free energy of activation per mole of the pure solvent and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ is the free energy of activation per mole of the solute. These were calculated¹⁷ with the help of following equations,

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#} = RT \ln (\Delta\bar{V}_1^0 / hN) \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_1^{0\#} + \frac{RT}{\bar{V}_1^0} [1000B - (\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)] \quad (8)$$

where h is the Plank constant, N is the Avagadro num-

ber, η_0 is the viscosity of the solvent, R is the gas constant and T is the absolute temperature.

The activation entropy for single and mixed electrolytes systems was obtained from the following relation¹⁶,

$$d(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#})/dT = -\Delta S_2^{0\#} \quad (9)$$

The enthalpy of activation $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ was calculated with the help of the following relation¹⁸

$$\Delta H_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_2^{0\#} + T\Delta S_2^{0\#} \quad (10)$$

The calculated value of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ for FA, DMF and DMSO are listed in Table 5. The values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ for single and mixed electrolytes systems are presented in Tables 6 and 7 respectively.

A perusal of Table 6 shows that the values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ for single bi-univalent electrolytes systems are larger than

Table 5. Values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ for non-aqueous solvents at different temperatures

Non-aqueous solvents	$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
FA	12.07	12.42	12.24
DMF	9.01	9.10	9.21
DMSO	10.86	10.98	11.18

Table 6. Values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ for bi-univalent single electrolyte systems in FA, DMF and DMSO at different temperatures

Electrolyte	$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
BaCl ₂ (FA)	35.95	33.29	32.95
MgCl ₂ (FA)	62.07	61.19	60.55
CoCl ₂ (FA)	60.54	59.25	58.06
SrCl ₂ (FA)	44.09	42.98	41.43
BaCl ₂ (DMSO)	34.47	33.26	31.26
NiCl ₂ (DMSO)	58.02	57.18	55.96
HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	18.22	16.66	15.60
SnCl ₂ (DMSO)	43.55	41.98	39.83
SrCl ₂ (DMSO)	41.23	40.07	38.83
MnCl ₂ (DMSO)	60.45	58.41	56.76
CoCl ₂ (DMSO)	58.41	57.29	56.22
CoCl ₂ (DMF)	49.42	48.24	47.27
MnCl ₂ (DMF)	51.05	49.81	48.22
ZnCl ₂ (DMF)	48.24	47.06	45.93
NiCl ₂ (DMF)	49.41	48.27	46.88
SnCl ₂ (DMF)	37.63	36.00	34.19

those of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ (vide Table 5). Thus for the single electrolyte systems in non-aqueous solvents, FA, DMF and DMSO ($\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$) > 0. From this it follows¹⁶, that these single electrolyte systems behave as structure makers in these non-aqueous solvents. On the other hand for the mixed electrolyte systems the values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ are negative in all the non-aqueous solvents. Therefore for these systems the quantity, ($\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$) < 0. From this it follows¹¹ that all the bi-univalent mixed electrolytes systems behave as structure breakers in non-aqueous solvents, FA, DMF and DMSO.

Recently, Zhang *et al.*¹⁹ have asserted that a positive value of coefficient *B* indicates the structure making capacity, while a negative one indicates the structure breaking capacity of the electrolytes. In the present study the values of *B* for single bi-univalent electrolyte systems are positive (Table 1), while for mixed bi-univalent electrolyte systems these are negative (Table 2). Thus our conclusions in regard to the structure making capacity of

single electrolyte systems and the structure breaking capacity of mixed electrolyte systems are in agreement with the views of Zhang *et al.*¹⁹.

The values of $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ for single and mixed bi-univalent electrolyte systems in FA, DMF and DMSO are presented in Tables 8 and 9 respectively. It is seen that for the solutions of bi-univalent single electrolyte systems in FA, DMF and DMSO the values of $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ are positive, in other words, the formation of the transition state is associated with bond-breaking and increase in order. This suggest that the slip-plane is somewhere in the region of centro-symmetric order¹⁶. On the other hand for mixed bi-univalent electrolyte systems, both $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ are negative; in other words the formation of transition state is associated with bond-making and an increase in order¹⁶. This suggests that the slip-plane is in the disordered region¹⁶.

Table 7. Values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ for bi-univalent mixed electrolyte systems in non-aqueous medium at different temperatures

Mixed electrolyte system	Ionic strength (<i>I</i>)	$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
		293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
BaCl ₂ + MgCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-140.93	-150.94	-164.79
SrCl ₂ + BaCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-105.30	-109.65	-126.68
CoCl ₂ + BaCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-105.89	-117.04	-133.33
CoCl ₂ + MgCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-77.41	-96.76	-113.28
SrCl ₂ + MgCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-62.23	-89.49	-95.59
SrCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-170.55	-179.40	-186.31
NiCl ₂ + BaCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-88.96	-131.92	-149.20
HgCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-48.51	-59.79	-121.48
CoCl ₂ + HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-97.66	-146.06	-159.59
NiCl ₂ + MnCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-29.40	-38.58	-77.01
SnCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-75.99	-119.13	-164.21
HgCl ₂ + MnCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-31.62	-37.06	-46.06
CoCl ₂ + SnCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-33.83	-54.57	-72.11
NiCl ₂ + SrCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-77.91	-121.09	-166.30
SrCl ₂ + HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-92.77	-104.65	-142.37
MnCl ₂ + SrCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-81.05	-111.47	-118.85
SnCl ₂ + HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-102.81	-149.17	-211.98
NiCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-42.09	-73.76	-103.63
MnCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-65.41	-68.11	-78.29
NiCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-57.06	-61.18	-71.11
ZnCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-40.86	-80.95	-116.32
ZnCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-91.61	-101.26	-152.83
SnCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-76.70	-92.88	-108.94
ZnCl ₂ + SnCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-74.55	-93.09	-97.75
SnCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-41.07	-24.48	-25.19

Table 8. Values of ($T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$) and ($\Delta H_2^{0\#}$) for bi-ivalent single electrolyte systems in FA, DMSO and DMF at different temperatures

Electrolyte	$T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)			$\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
BaCl ₂ (FA)	43.95	45.45	46.95	79.90	78.74	79.90
MgCl ₂ (FA)	22.18	22.93	23.69	84.24	84.13	84.24
CoCl ₂ (FA)	36.46	37.70	38.94	97.00	96.95	97.00
SrCl ₂ (FA)	38.94	40.26	41.59	83.02	83.25	83.02
BaCl ₂ (DMSO)	47.12	48.72	50.33	81.59	81.98	81.59
NiCl ₂ (DMSO)	30.24	31.27	32.30	88.26	88.45	88.26
HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	38.38	39.69	41.00	56.60	56.35	56.60
SnCl ₂ (DMSO)	54.51	56.37	58.23	98.06	98.35	98.06
SrCl ₂ (DMSO)	35.11	36.31	37.50	76.34	76.37	76.34
MnCl ₂ (DMSO)	54.09	55.93	57.78	114.54	114.34	114.54
CoCl ₂ (DMSO)	32.16	33.26	34.35	90.57	90.55	90.57
CoCl ₂ (DMF)	31.53	32.60	33.68	80.95	80.84	80.95
MnCl ₂ (DMF)	41.46	42.87	44.28	92.50	92.68	92.50
ZnCl ₂ (DMF)	33.80	34.95	36.10	82.03	82.01	82.03
NiCl ₂ (DMF)	37.14	38.41	39.67	86.55	86.67	86.55
SnCl ₂ (DMF)	50.48	52.20	53.93	88.11	88.20	88.11

Table 9. Values of ($T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$) and ($\Delta H_2^{0\#}$) for bi-ivalent mixed electrolyte systems in FA, DMSO and DMF at different temperatures

Mixed electrolyte system	Ionic strength (<i>I</i>)	$T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)			$\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
		293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
BaCl ₂ + MgCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-349.80	-361.73	-73.66	-490.73	-512.67	-538.46
SrCl ₂ + BaCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-313.27	-323.95	-334.64	-418.57	-433.60	-461.32
CoCl ₂ + BaCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-402.10	-415.82	-429.53	-507.99	-532.86	-562.86
CoCl ₂ + MgCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-525.68	-543.61	-561.54	-603.09	-640.37	-674.82
SrCl ₂ + MgCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-489.00	-505.68	-522.37	-551.23	-595.17	-617.96
SrCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (FA)	1.5	-230.99	-238.87	-246.75	-401.54	-418.26	-433.06
NiCl ₂ + BaCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-883.01	-913.14	-943.26	-971.97	-1045.06	-1092.46
HgCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-1069.67	-1106.16	-1142.65	-1118.18	-1165.95	-1264.13
CoCl ₂ + HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-907.71	-938.67	-969.64	-1005.37	-1084.73	-1129.23
NiCl ₂ + MnCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-697.83	-721.64	-745.44	-727.24	-760.21	-822.46
SnCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-1293.19	-1337.30	-1381.41	-1369.17	-1456.43	-1545.63
HgCl ₂ + MnCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-211.58	-218.80	-226.02	-243.21	-255.86	-272.08
CoCl ₂ + SnCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-561.09	-580.23	-599.37	-594.91	-634.80	-671.47
NiCl ₂ + SrCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-1295.60	-1339.80	-1384.00	-1373.51	-1460.89	-1550.29
SrCl ₂ + HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-726.96	-751.76	-776.55	-819.73	-856.40	-918.92
MnCl ₂ + SrCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-553.99	-572.88	-591.78	-635.04	-684.36	-710.63
SnCl ₂ + HgCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-1600.17	-1654.75	-1709.34	-1702.98	-1803.92	-1921.32
NiCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMSO)	0.6	-902.02	-932.79	-963.56	-944.11	-1006.56	-1067.19
MnCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-188.86	-195.30	-201.74	-254.26	-263.40	-280.03
NiCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-205.90	-212.93	-219.95	-262.97	-274.11	-291.06
ZnCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-1105.97	-1143.69	-1181.42	-1146.83	-1224.64	-1297.74
ZnCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-897.32	-927.93	-958.54	-988.94	-1029.19	-1111.37
SnCl ₂ + CoCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-472.56	-488.68	-504.80	-549.25	-581.56	-613.73
ZnCl ₂ + SnCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-340.05	-351.65	-363.25	-414.60	-444.75	-461.00
SnCl ₂ + NiCl ₂ (DMF)	0.6	-232.70	-240.64	-248.58	191.63	216.16	223.38

Experimental

All the electrolytes were B.D.H. products of analytical reagent grade and were used as such without further purification, after drying over anhydrous calcium chloride in a desiccator for 24 h. The non-aqueous solvents; formamide (FA), dimethyl formamide (DMF) and dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) were also of B.D.H. (A.R.) grade and were used as such.

Densities were measured by using 5 ml pycnometers. The volumes of pycnometers were calibrated with deionised and doubly distilled water at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K. The densities of single and mixed electrolyte systems in FA, DMF and DMSO were determined from the mass of the solution in the pycnometer after reaching thermal equilibrium with a water bath at the studied temperatures. A Mettler electronic balance with an accuracy of $\pm 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$ g was used for the mass determination.

Viscosities were measured with a calibrated U-type Ostwald's viscometer with sufficiently long efflux time to avoid kinetic energy correction. Temperatures were controlled by a thermostatic water bath fluctuating to ± 0.01 K. The uncertainty of calculated absolute viscosities was $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ mPa.s.

The apparent molar volumes of single and bi-univalent electrolyte systems in FA, DMF and DMSO were determined using the following equation²⁰,

$$V_{\phi} = \frac{1000(\rho_0 - \rho)}{C\rho_0} + \frac{M}{\rho_0} \quad (11)$$

The apparent molar volumes (V_{ϕ}) of bi-univalent mixed electrolytes systems in FA, DMF and DMSO were determined as a function of fraction (y) of ionic strength due to the first electrolyte in the mixture of two electrolytes at different temperatures (keeping the ionic strength of the system constant) using the following equation¹⁴,

$$V_{\phi} = \frac{1000(\rho_0 - \rho)}{C\rho_0} + \frac{\bar{M}}{\rho_0} \quad (12)$$

where ρ_0 and ρ are densities of solvent and solutions respectively and C is total molarity of the solution. \bar{M} is the effective molecular weight of the mixed electrolyte system given by following equation¹⁴,

$$\bar{M} = \frac{n_1M_1 + n_2M_2}{n_1 + n_2} \quad (13)$$

where n_1 and n_2 are the number of moles and M_1 and M_2 are the molecular weights of first and second electrolyte respectively.

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